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HORIZON 2020 IMPTOX PERSPECTIVE

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Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are pervasive environmental pollutants found in marine water, freshwater, agroecosystems, atmosphere, food, drinking water, and biota. Despite their widespread presence, comprehensive data on MNPs prevalence and impact remain limited due to analytical challenges. Beyond their physical presence, MNPs carry adsorbed contaminants such as organic pollutants, heavy metals, and microbes, raising concerns about their potential health risks.

The European Union's Horizon 2020 Imptox project – “An innovative analytical platform to investigate the effect and toxicity of micro and nanoplastics combined with environmental contaminants on the risk of allergic disease in preclinical and clinical studies” - under the European Research Cluster to understand the health impacts of micro and nanoplastics (CUSP), consists of consortium of 12 partners from 8 European countries, and addresses these concerns by focusing on the indirect hazards of MNPs, specifically through adsorbed contaminants like allergenic proteins, pathogenic bacteria, and combined hazards. Allergies, affecting over 150 million Europeans, are on the rise, with predictions indicating that half the EU population may be affected by 2025. Understanding whether environmental MNPs contribute to this increase is critical. Project key objectives include the production and characterization of high-quality in-house MNPs, development of protocols for biological material digestion, innovative labeling for NPs tracking, and the conduct of large-scale environmental studies and a clinical trial on pediatric exposure assessment. Imptox aims to improve our understanding of MNPs exposure through ingestion and inhalation, provide risk assessment scenarios, inform policy, and enhance communication strategies between scientists and stakeholders. By focusing on vulnerable populations and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, Imptox will contribute to societal, health, and environmental advancements.

Keywords: microplastics, proteomics, allergies, pollution, health

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